

NARRATIVES OF THE TEACHERS IN GEOGRAPHICALLY ISOLATED AND DISADVANTAGED AREAS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12699796>

ABSTRACT

This study entitled “Narratives of the Teachers in Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas” aimed to depict the stories of the teachers in far-flung schools, their coping strategies, and insights towards policy formulations and interventions for schools in remote areas. The qualitative-descriptive phenomenological approach was used. The data were collected from 8 teachers in GIDA elementary schools of South Upi, Maguindanao. One-on-one interviews and Focus-Group Discussions (FGD) were used by the researcher to gather the data. Employing thematic analysis of data revealed that far-flung teachers had various experiences and defined them as the Yin and Yang of Teacher’s Life. These consist of two sub-themes arduous journey of the teachers in the far-flung school which refers to struggles and difficult experiences; and light and hope in the midst of struggle which describes the positive and light experiences. The far-flung teachers cited their coping strategies which described them as social support system that relates to the support they get from the parents, community, agencies, and concerned partners; problem-solving strategy which refers to practical solutions to problems; acceptance and devotion to work tell the teacher’s dedication; and burning desire to help the entire community.

Keywords: *Narratives, Experiences, Coping Strategy, Insights, Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas, Far-flung Areas, GIDA, aspirations, motivations, Geographically Challenged Schools*

INTRODUCTION

The 1987 Philippine Constitution, Article XIV, Sec. 1 stated that the state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. Apparently, in the Philippines, the number of out-of-school youth rose at the onset of the pandemic from 16.9 percent in January 2020 to 25.2 percent three months later in April 2020, based on a study released by the US Agency for International Development in November 2021 (Bautista, 2022).

Quality education is what we believe to be our foundation for a good future. However, not all children are assured of a good education and therefore, a good future. This has been a challenge for children living in far-flung areas who face different difficulties in going to school – such as walking great lengths to reach their destination, including going up the mountains or crossing rivers and lakes. For children living in far-flung areas, receiving quality instruction as well as education appears to be an extensive shot as they contend with a lack of resources.

In the context of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), teachers from all over the region intensively embarked on providing quality education as it is one of the 12-point agenda of the Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) - “No Bangsamoro Child Left Behind” in terms of access to quality and relevant educational services. As of August 2022, the department recorded at least 918, 621 learners in BARMM (DepEd, 2022). Furthermore, the World Bank (2019) found out also that, out-of-school youth and adults have thus accumulated over the generations in BARMM – almost 45% of 16-30 years old are out-of-school in BARMM, double the national average. In response to the regional mandate and to reach every child across the region, schools have been established even in remote areas. The teachers assigned to these schools have distinct and diverse experiences and stories worthy of being told, shared, and heard. Brillantes & Nebria, (2021) described that most of them (teachers) felt struggled and were challenged in arriving at the school, knowing they will be assigned to schools that are really on top of the mountains.

The Department of Health (DOH) defines geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas or GIDA as communities with marginalized populations, physically and socio-economically separated from mainstream society. It can be due to physical factors such as distance, weather conditions, transportation difficulties (island, upland, lowland, landlocked, hard-to-reach, and unserved and underserved communities), or socio-economic factors like high poverty incidence, presence of vulnerable factors or communities in or recovering from the situation of crisis or armed conflict.

Additionally, South Upi Municipality is a fourth-class municipality with 46,342 hectares (MENR, 2022) total land mass area. It consists of only eleven (11) barangays and there were still areas within that are isolated and difficult to access. Yet, there were schools built in these areas to reach more learners and make education more accessible to all, and apparently, these realities shaped the impression that teachers in the area were

burdened to travel to and from the nearest accessible roads. Similarly, Quejada and Orale (2018), described teaching in remote schools as a huge challenge. Although, given the challenges faced by the teachers, they still found a reason to keep going, (Hipolito, 2022). Thus, teachers are intrinsically motivated, passionate, and committed to providing much-needed educational services in these isolated areas. The above-cited realities faced by the teachers in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas led the researcher to find out their experiences and the coping strategies in teaching with the challenges they've encountered.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to explore teachers' narratives in the Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Area (GIDA) of South Upi District. Particularly, this study sought to find answers to the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the teachers in the Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Area (GIDA)?
2. What are the coping strategies used by the teachers in facing the challenges encountered?
3. What are the insights of the teachers on policy formulations and interventions for schools in GIDA?

Narrative as an arts-based inquiry is simply an elegant and exceptionally useful way to uncover nuance and detail about previous experiences. Narrative inquiry is not simply storytelling; it is a method of inquiry that uses storytelling to uncover nuance. Stories heal and soothe the body and spirit, providing hope and courage to explore and grow. The process of storytelling, a fundamental element in narrative inquiry, provides the opportunity for dialogue and reflection, each intertwined and cyclical (Wang & Geale, 2015). Genuinely, the stories of these teachers, their joys, and their pains in teaching in geographically challenged communities of South Upi are worthy of being heard and shared at this time. In return, these reflections of experience will serve as a solid background of knowledge for teachers and effectively use this knowledge in the art and science of teaching. As affirmed by Hipolito (2022), allowing the teachers to recollect their stories enables them to look clearly into their experience, determine the challenges that arise, think of strategies to overcome them next time, investigate other possibilities, and accumulate lessons that will make them stronger and better prepared.

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative descriptive phenomenological design. This approach was employed to gain deeper insights into how we will understand the teachers' experiences in geographically isolated places in South Upi, as well as how they cope with the challenges of their experiences as teachers. The participants were allowed to converse about their perceptions freely and comfortably. Focus-group discussion and an

interview were employed using guide questions to ensure that the discussions stayed on track. In this phenomenology study, the researcher was responsible for formulating an interview guide to elicit answers to the research questions. Correspondingly, the interview guide was submitted to content and face validation by experts. The researcher used purposive sampling to identify the participants of this study. Eight (8) far-flung teachers in South Upi District were subjected to an interview. These teachers were assigned to schools that were classified as far-flung schools and were geographically distant from each other. The researcher collected the data by himself. Responses were recorded, coded, and later transcribed. In analyzing the data, the researcher rigorously followed the six phases of thematic analysis such as 1) familiarization; 2) coding; 3) generating themes; 4) reviewing themes; 5) defining and naming themes; and 6) reporting (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Caufield, 2019). In naming themes, these were phrased concisely and were made punchy to give the reader a sense of what the theme is all about (Braun and Clarke, 2006). There were also communication letters explaining the conduct of the study to participants of the study to give information about the research, seek consent, and at the same time set an appointment for a one-on-one discussion and a focus group discussion. Participants were given codes such as Teacher A, Teacher B, and so on to achieve confidentiality in the responses they made. An audio recorder was used to record the insights, perspectives, and reflections of the participants but with their consent to ensure the veracity of the statements given. In this way, it ensured the correctness and success of the manuscript to be produced. The researcher also conducted Focus Group Discussions to gather further evidence on their experiences as a teacher in far-flung schools. This further established a variety of standpoints and perspectives that deeply enhanced and supported the study which cannot be accomplished only by merely one-on-one interviews. This study was purely narratives in nature. Wang et.al (2017) described that stories can serve as a primary means for understanding the pattern of an individual life.

RESULTS

Table I. Experiences of Teachers in Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Experiences of Teachers 1. Distance and the Difficulty of Transportation 2. Bad weather conditions (Storms/typhoons) that caused rivers and creeks to flood 3. GIDA is left out of the latest trend 4. Lack of Classrooms and enough supply of other resources 5. Insufficient books, no paper and pencils 6. Poor physical status of the buildings 7. Limited instructional materials available 8. Multigrade classes due to lack of teachers	1. Geographical Location of the School 2. Situations in GIDA 3. Inadequate facilities 4. Lack of Teachers

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9. There are few people in the areas, and houses are typically far from each other 10. Many Pupils but with only a few teachers teaching in the school 11. Low Remuneration of Volunteer Teachers teaching in GIDA 12. Parents have limited to no educational background 13. Parents have no stable job 14. Parents depend on teachers 15. Learners are slow learners 16. Teaching learners the basics of 3R's 17. Level down the difficulty of the topics 18. Teaching the sound of a particular letter in grade 5 class 19. Low self-esteem of learners 20. Parents cannot assist their children with their schoolwork 21. Difficulty in Communication 22. Different cultural orientations between teachers and learners 23. Translations of the lesson into the learner's mother tongue 24. Community love and care 25. Supportive Parents 26. Learning while working 27. Adapted to the lifestyle in a remote area 28. Learner's success makes teachers in GIDA happy and accomplished 29. Helping far-flung learners 30. No overage learners in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Less populated areas 6. Huge Class Populations 7. Low salary 8. Lack of Education or Illiterate Parents 9. Poor Socio-economic 10. Due to no education parents depend on teachers for their errands 11. Slow learners 12. Pupils Low Educational Performance 13. Linguistic barrier between teachers and learners 14. Learners are used to their mother tongue 15. Community Support/Parents supports 16. Prospect for growth 17. The joy of seeing pupils' dreams come true
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Table 1 revealed that the narrations of the teachers in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas of South Upi were a combination of positive and difficult experiences. The distance of walking or horse-riding made their life challenging in the far-flung areas. The situation was even more difficult during bad weather conditions like heavy rains, storms or typhoons, and even flash floods. Teachers also claimed that GIDA schools are being left out by the latest educational trends. More than that, schools were also confronted with classroom shortages, oversized class populations, insufficient learning materials, low compensation or remuneration for volunteer teachers, teacher shortages, language barriers, underachieved learners, and even illiterate parents. However, these teachers also narrated positive experiences they encountered such as

the amount of support they got from the parents and the community in school-related activities and programs, their positive experiences are made up of the learning they derived from their situations because of the hardships they encountered which served as an opportunity for them to grow and develop, their ability to accustom from the lifestyle of the school they are assigned to, and the bizarre feeling of joy seeing their learners succeed or accomplished something inspires them to do better in teaching.

Table II. The Coping Strategies Used by the Teachers in Facing the Challenges Encountered

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
<p>Coping Strategies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Strengthening Parent-Teacher Association 2. Parents support teachers not just in school activity but also outside including their transportation 3. Attend relevant training to improve teaching strategies 4. Referred to past teachers or administrators on their techniques while they were still in GIDA 5. Coordination with the BLGU and LGU 6. Teachers focused on teaching 3R's (Reading, Writing, and 'Rithmetic) to their slow learners 7. Utilized readily available books 8. Surf online for learning materials 9. Teaching requires sacrifices 10. Teachers having the same culture and language can easily cope 11. Loving one work and doing your best in teaching is one way to cope 12. Having pledged to teach and knowing the nature of a teaching career 13. At the end of the day, learners must have something to learn 14. Help the IP learners to learn since it is the teachers' responsibility to do it 15. It is God's way to be assigned in the remote areas 16. Family is also a source of motivation for teachers to teach in the area 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Parent and Community Support 2. Training and Seminars provided by NGOs and MBHTE 3. Learning from the past 4. Linkages and Partnerships 5. Problem Solving 6. To solve problems of inadequate teaching and learning materials teachers surf the internet for online sources available 7. Teachers' devotion to a teaching career 8. Passion 9. Burning Desire to Help the learners and community

This table shows the coping strategies used by the teachers in facing the challenges they encountered in teaching. To deal with the challenges, the teachers strengthened the Parent-Teacher Association and maximized their potential for the benefit of the school, teachers let the association facilitate the project toward its completion. Parents' support was shown not just inside the school premises, but even with the

teachers' transportation they helped teachers cross rivers successfully. The result also shows that training and other professional development activities are beneficial for teachers to improve themselves to be even more responsive to the needs of their learners. They established strong partnerships with BLGU and LGU to gain more support. On the matter of learners' academic performance, the teachers focused on the 3Rs – reading, writing, and arithmetic. In the same way, teachers utilized online materials to resolve the developing concerns on textbooks and other learning. A teaching career in the GIDA involves sacrifices which means you must endure all the discomforts and struggles just to deliver the educational services needed by the learners. They also shared that loving what they are doing, being passionate about what they do in the remote areas and having pledged to a teaching career have helped them cope with the challenges they experienced. Teachers who are Indigenous People easily cope in geographically challenged areas, they narrated that they wanted to educate their co-IPs and have an education just like what they had. More than just an assignment, teachers looked at it as God's divine provision to teach in GIDA, they believed that God had purposely led them in this life because they could be of great help. Family is one factor also that motivates teachers assigned to GIDA.

Table III indicates the insights, recommendations, and aspirations of the teachers based on their experiences. This shows that they recommend additional teachers seeing that one major problem they encounter is the lack of teachers, additional classrooms, more learning resources, infrastructure like bridges, road constructions for easy transportation, and electrification in GIDA schools. Teachers' aspirations involved promotion, transfer to nearby accessible schools, salary increase, and benefits like hazard pay. Their source of motivation includes the situations of the people, and the learners in the area, their family became one of their motivations to teach in GIDA.

Table III. Insights, Recommendations, and Aspirations of the Teachers in GIDA

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
<p>Insights, Recommendations, and Aspirations of the Teachers in GIDA</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Deployment of regular teachers in GIDA 2. Add more teachers with the same cultural backgrounds as the community 3. School building renovations 4. The makeshift classroom building must be replaced with a permanent and concrete school building 5. Provision of Learning Materials 6. Prioritization of GIDA in terms of teaching and learning materials 7. Computers to keep abreast with the technological advancement 8. Bridge construction 9. Road improvements or construction 10. Electrification project in schools 11. Be given a chance for Teachers' promotion 12. Transfer to a nearby schools 13. Increase Volunteer teacher's honorarium 14. Hazard pays 15. Helping the learners in the area made the teachers stay in GIDA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Additional Teachers 2. Additional Classrooms 3. Learning Materials or Resources 4. Infrastructure 5. Career Advancement/Progress 6. Salary Increase 7. Noble Intentions

DISCUSSION

Theme I: Experiences of the Teachers in Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas

The following are emerging themes summarized by the researcher based on the narratives of the teacher-participants of their experiences.

I.1. Yin and Yang of Teacher's Life

This theme characterizes the experiences of the teachers in far-flung schools of South Upi. This theme appeared predominantly in the responses gathered from the

participants, as some of them described their experiences to be challenging but truly rewarding as they also experienced positivity amid adversities.

Just as the *yin and yang* symbol that describes everything in life has two opposite sides, we must maintain it balanced to work on both sides pleasantly. Teachers in far-flung schools are flooded with stories of struggles that can almost succumb to their chosen profession but having looked at their stories of successes, inspired and motivated them to go further and become resilient enough for the learners, parents, and the community in general.

Far-flung teachers revealed diverse stories they encountered and were classified into two sub-themes such as the arduous journey of the teachers in the far-flung schools, and light and hope in the midst of struggles. The sub-themes that emerge based on the common answers were presented in the succeeding discussions.

I.1.1. Arduous Journey of the Teachers in the Far-flung Schools

This sub-theme is the shady experiences of the teachers. It describes the pains, struggles, dilemmas, and tough experiences of teachers in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas. A teaching career is one of the noblest and most rewarding professions. It requires the ability to do more with less, dedication, and passion, and it takes a lot of patience to become a real one. In this study, far-flung teachers cited innumerable obstacles, dangers, or risks they must face just to reach their school assignments. These difficulties were grouped into categories and were given names based on the narratives of the teacher-participants provided. These are the following: school setting, inadequate facilities, teachers' unavailability, illiterate parents, teachers' low salary, pupils' learning status, and linguistic barrier.

School Setting

The school setting refers to the geographical location of the school. Basically, it includes the distance, means of transportation, time spent traveling to school, weather conditions as well as a description of the school's location. It came out in the conversations that six (6) of the far-flung teachers were concerned with the distance, they must travel for it's too risky and tiring.

With a serious face, *Teacher A* said "My experience as a teacher in GIDA is "*yung sobrang layo ng school sa bahay*" you need to hike more or less two hours before you reach the school. Then sometimes when there are storms or typhoons, you have to cross the river even when it floods." Apart from heavy rains, typhoons, or floods, these teachers also had to endure the scorching heat of the sun when they traversed the rugged road to school. Fundamentally, teachers in far-flung must be resistant enough to be able to reach the schools where they are assigned.

Teacher E lightly noted "I started [teaching in a far-flung school] as a volunteer. [Back then] I had to walk for a 1-kilometer distance from home to school. So, it is really hard due to financial needs. I had to cross a river and during heavy rains, it scared me because the river cannot be crossed if it flooded. Due to distance also, I have to bring my food for a day." Typically, these rivers do not have any bridges to use when they flood. The teachers at times may wait for the floods

to subside and or even look for someone in the community to help them cross river floods because most of the people beside the rivers have already developed a technique or strategy to cross the river even when it floods.

While tapping the table *Teacher H* articulated, “As a teacher, I have so many experiences encountered every time I went to school. First, the road is very challenging and very far [that is 25 kilometers from the highway], and in heavy rain, we don’t have a choice but to walk if there is no horse available. When there’s a flood, we don’t have the choice [too] but to cross it. All of that is really difficult.” Aside from that, the teachers experienced life-threatening instances in the pursuit of this noble calling – teaching. Holding hands with one another to cross heavy floods that even caused their lives at stake. This supports the statement of Barcena (2018) that teaching in a remote school is a huge challenge. Teachers would encounter a variety of uncomfortable means of transportation like “*banka*,” “*habal-habal*,” and even the use of animals such as horses or carabao just to reach the station.

Looking at a distant space, *Teacher C* retorted “Yes [sir], I have so many difficult experiences [sir!] ...when we say GIDA, my first impression is that [ang lugar] ay napag-iwanan na ng kabihasan. What I mean is the transportation and communication were too difficult.” This participant is insistent and certain of his answer that what troubled him in GIDA are the means of transportation and communication which refers to lack of cellphone signal or internet connection which could possibly affect the teaching and learning process. These statements support the study of Lariosa et.al. (2022) who described the lives of the teachers in far-flung schools are challenged to work out of their comfort zone and to deal with students and communities with different cultures. They employed different strategies for adaptation that helped them survive and stay in far-flung areas. Their situation as far-flung teachers is not as easy as others had narrated.

Moreover, *Teacher F* distinctly cited while looking outside the window that “The distance is really a big challenge, especially during bad weather specifically on the portion of the river because it’s too deep and the road is one more thing. You have to literally push [lift] your motorcycle because there are portions that are really difficult sir!” This phenomenon is consistent with Leocadio (2023) which emphasizes that teachers in far-flung areas often face security risks. They may work in areas that are prone to conflict, natural disasters, or other dangers. In some cases, they may even be at risk of being robbed at gunpoint or experiencing violence. This means that teachers in these areas need to be vigilant and take extra precautions to ensure their safety.

In addition, *Teacher B* anxiously answered “First, hiking is really difficult when you are assigned to far-flung school areas.” What makes it difficult [sir] is the road going to my school assignment. You [will] need [also] to bring your allowance [food & financial] for a month.” Considering the road to far-flung schools and the weather conditions that the teachers encountered, only a few can be attracted to this kind of situation.

These statements confirmed the study of Hipolito (2022) who found out that the rugged road made it troublesome for teachers to reach the school. Things get worse when the weather is not fine. The same is true with Gallego (2022) who

mentioned that a group of teachers also claimed that they must cross three overflowing rivers to reach the school, while others have to walk 23 hours traversing a slippery and boggy road, and there are times they encounter venomous animals along the way to school.

Inadequate facilities

Inadequate facilities pertain to the needs of teachers for classrooms, and/or teaching and learning facilities. It comprised their experiences of not having enough classrooms, teaching, and learning materials that are essential to pupils learning.

With a sense of disappointment and frustration, *Teacher H* said, “We also lack classrooms, and I must say all the resources are not enough. I don’t even know exactly how I am going to cater to 315 learners in a limited space.” The needs for the classroom may only depend on the class size that the teachers have at hand. If the class size is too big, the teachers may just accommodate them (learners) anyway even with the uncomfortable conditions. However, the benefits of a conducive setting are evident as it allows for an independent exchange of ideas, opinions, judgments, and skills between the teachers and learners to achieve the expected educational outcome by considering the physical, psychological, social, and cultural needs of all the learners. For many far-flung teachers, providing the learners with a conducive space is a monumental effort and tedious to consider.

Teacher E looked at me straight and softly answered “Yes, like an inadequate classroom. When the winds blew hard or heavy rains [back then], we came out of the classroom because its foundation is just made of bamboo trees, and we were afraid it would collapse. Also, books are insufficient, I [teacher] am the only one who has a book. For pupils, they don’t have enough learning materials like paper and pencils. So literally, how can you teach them in this kind of situation? [no papers or no pencil].” Consequently, the community where these far-flung schools are poor, and they can barely go to the market to buy school supplies for their children. Teachers most of the time provide their learners with paper or pencils at their expense just for learning to take place.

On another note, *Teacher C* already has in mind that he can encounter many difficulties as he forthrightly verbalized “At first, it was very hard for me. The first thing that bothers my mind is [the question that] can I make it? I mean how can I survive in a school where I can perform my profession? My first impression is that a lot of problems I could encounter such as the physical status of the school...” Sadly, teachers have to build up and enforce their creativity and talents to make the school engaging for learners to learn.

Generally, in far-flung schools, it is expected that the buildings were just makeshift or PTA-initiated buildings that served as temporary learning spaces for teachers and learners while waiting for government-funded school buildings.

With eagerness, *Teacher A* declared “As a teacher in GIDA, there are lots of challenges, issues, and difficulties. Such as the teaching tools and the slow learners. You have to level down [standards] what you teach to them.” It is believed that teaching tools support the teaching process to achieve better outcomes. Apparently, these materials were insufficient.

These statements were found congruent with Gallego (2022) that due to inadequate facilities and resources teachers are devising new approaches to deliver the education that our students seek. Teachers need to live with the different barriers that they face. Some of them even shared some of their resources with their students.

In the same way, it was further supported by Castigador (2019) that teachers shared a portion of their salary to acquire teaching and learning resources in the classroom.

Teachers Unavailability

This part describes the dilemma of teachers in far-flung schools relating to the lack of teachers who will facilitate the learning necessities of the area. Teachers had to double their responsibilities as classroom teachers and at the same time school heads. In this study, two (2) of the teacher-participants were performing the duties of a teacher and a school head. The school barely even gets an additional teacher.

Correspondingly, *Teacher F* agreed “There are so many challenges and difficulties I encounter. If we speak about [challenges and issues confronting] teaching and learning, one is the lack of teachers because we are multigrade.” A multigrade set-up was made due to teacher shortage. There are not enough teachers to facilitate the teaching and learning procedure. Other schools have tried utilizing the aid of volunteer teachers. However, due to the far distance and limited salary they received from the barangay and LGU, they stay only from one to two or five years, as the maximum.

A cheery *Teacher H* pedantically shared “Reaching the school, I cannot even explain what I’m gonna do there [school], there are no people around the school, no nearby houses too, what tribe or kind of youth am I gonna teach? All I thought was, we have few pupils only but to my surprise they crowd during class. We have 315 learners with only 2 regular teachers and 3 volunteer teachers.” Surprisingly, an increasing number of learners caused a shortage of teachers.

The number of teachers facilitating and delivering learning in far-flung communities is truly a problem. These narrations were analogous to a news article that, one of the perennial problems in the Philippines particularly basic education is the teachers. This concern is worse in many rural and far-flung areas such as the scarcity of schools but even if there is a school with available classrooms in neighboring barangays, there is a scarcity of qualified teachers to reckon with (Sun Star Pampanga, 2017).

Teachers’ Low Salary

This portion pronounces the challenges experienced by teachers on their salary as volunteer teachers. They shared that it is very low to the extent that they can’t even afford their personal needs.

With a deep sigh, *Teacher E* said, “During my volunteer days, my finances cannot even suffice for my personal needs just like “*sabon*”, *mga* “shampoo”. In two months, I am only receiving 500 pesos as remuneration. But because of my

willingness to serve [IP communities], and to prove myself in this profession, I was able to manage all of that.” The great determination of this teacher helped her handle the difficult situation brought about by poor compensation.

In addition, *Teacher A* looked down and shared “It became a challenge for me as a [volunteer] teacher in the distant communities, the low salary I received.” Truthfully, volunteer teachers contribute enormous help to remote and isolated areas. Since there are insufficient regular teachers assigned in the far-to-reach schools. Yet, they are not given due recognition and proper compensation for their efforts.

It appears that the incentive is one of the things that brings these teachers frustration because it is not sufficient for their daily needs. At times due to pupils’ quality of life in the place, they even have to use personal resources for learning materials and teaching tools. Purportedly, providing these teachers with appropriate funding can stimulate their commitment to work and lessen their burden. This impression is the same with Leocadia (2023) who specified that the dedication of teachers working under difficult conditions and making significant sacrifices to provide education to marginalized communities, recognizing their contributions, and providing them with appropriate incentives helped attract and retain talented teachers in these areas.

In addition, the statements were analogous to Lariosa et.al (2022) who pointed out that teachers were encouraged by the learners’ situation, that love of the profession even goes to the extent of taking part in their inadequate salary for classroom use and making it conducive for learning. Another form of motivation was monetary grants, which helped them stay at the assigned station.

Illiterate Parents

This situation includes the difficulties faced by teachers regarding the kind of life that the community in the remote areas has. Parents are uneducated as reflected in three of the teacher-participants which resulted in a lack of support for their children’s academics as well as an inactive participation in school-related activities.

With an expression of sadness, *Teacher H* explained that “Parents are uneducated. Sometimes when they have some documents or papers to process [such as birth certificates, marriage contracts, or even certifications from barangay and etc.] *ma’am pwede mo kami tulungan sa ganito...* So, through that, we can be of help.” This participant has addressed not just the learning gaps that the place really needs. She showed so humility by giving her expertise to parents who are also uneducated. These parents have not gone to school before due to their geographical locations.

Unpromisingly, *Teacher A* explained that part of his motivation to teach is the IP learners as “most of their parents are purely dependent on teachers [because] they lack the necessary knowledge, and others cannot even write.” It came out from the discussion that most parents are having their “thumbmarks” instead of their signatures in many cases in school such as attendance during school meetings. This scenario is very well-known for teachers in far-flung areas.

Commonly, the given instances opened the way to greater and tougher situations that teachers have come across within the area. On the other side, the lack of education among parents could result in economic matters.

With a troubled impression, *Teacher D* shortly described that “Most parents are uneducated and don’t have a stable job.” Emphasizing that having little to no educational background at all will automatically conduce to unstable employment and financial incapability.

This result ties in well with the statements of Sy (2021) that the situation in GIDAs is far from ideal. Quejada & Orale (2018) mentioned that geographically isolated communities are usually poor. The school, the students, and the community exhibit poverty. The result also affirmed the study of Lariosa, Diendo, and Espinosa (2022) that isolated communities are usually deprived. The area lacks so many things. Most households served are penurious, parents have low educational backgrounds, and some have not gone to school.

Pupils’ Learning Status

This illustration labels the learning status of learners in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas. From the data given, the status of their learning is dissatisfying. Comparatively, learners in the isolated areas were slow learners and they were underperform compared to the learners in urban areas or accessible schools, particularly near the highways. Six (6) of the teacher-participants have parallel experiences concerning this area.

Indirectly, *Teacher H* uttered “For the learners, we teach them how to read and write. Just the simple [basic] one because you have to level your [teaching] standards to them [learners] for learning to take place.” Ideally, the contents to be taught by the teachers should be based on the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) or the prescribed curriculum content of the DepEd but due to the prevailing needs of the learners and also bearing in mind the learning capabilities of the learners in the area, you have to begin first with what is basic, essential, and significant. This way, it prepared the learners for much more complex lessons in the future.

Significantly, *Teacher A* has the same story, he stated that next to his difficulties as a GIDA teacher are the slow learners, he is handling. He further noted that “you have to level down what you teach to them. For instance, I’m a grade 5 teacher but we’re still on sounding letters of the alphabet.” Seeing most of his learners to be underperformed, this participant has developed his technique and style of teaching. Most of the pupils have delayed cognitive aspects due to impoverishment and limited access to other sources of learning.

Moreover, *Teacher D* expressively remarked that “Children are used to being *mahiyain* and some of them are slow learners. Some of them do not participate in school activities. Some are unhealthy and [have] fewer opportunities [in life].” Tëduray are known to be shy and timid however adding the fact that they are slow learners is painful to note. They barely have access to basic services and various opportunities in life.

An extremely keen *Teacher E* detailed that “I also experienced parents who neglect their child’s attendance during their Kindergarten to Grade Three [level/stages]. This resulted in learners being academically weak in their higher grades – Grades Four to Six. Wherein, supposedly this is the foundation, right? So, in my observation, it resulted in them becoming slow learners. Those who were properly monitored [supervised] by their parents were the ones who are good in class too. Parents’ involvement is a must.” Slow learners are associated with various factors. The learners do not have enough supply of learning materials, and poverty, parents’ educational background. In some cases, schools in the far-flung areas are also multigrade. However, in the locale of this study, teachers were able to get the aid of volunteer teachers.

Slow learners are just one of the difficult situations that teachers have to bear in remote areas. These statements confirm the study of Quejada and Orale (2018) which says that classes are multi-grade and have many slow learners and non-readers due to the confluence of many factors primarily due to poverty. With committed teachers, they produce few achievers.

Linguistic Barrier

Four of the teacher-participants experienced language barriers and described it as one of their challenges in the geographically challenged community. Here are some of the transcriptions:

Teacher F articulated that “Sometimes teachers and learners didn’t understand each other because they are purely *Maguindanaon* in Letingan ES.” Communication between learners and teachers happens only when there is a language common to both parties. If barriers arise in terms of language usually the teachers must adapt or learn the language of the children so learning will most likely happen.

With certainty, *Teacher C* mentioned that dealing with Pupils who are *Tëduray* is one of his problems encountered. He stated “My first impression is that a lot of problems I could encounter such as... dealing with pupils who are *Tëduray* for which I am an *Ilonggo* and how to deal with parents and the community as a whole. In the beginning [sir], I don’t really know how to speak [communicate in] *Tëduray*. So, there are times that I use words that have an opposite meaning in their dialect. Just like, “*Sut gom!*” what I meant was “Come inside the classroom”. However, I wondered why they’d come out of the classroom. So, only to find out that what I actually said was for them to come out. So that is my first encounter sir, with the language barrier between me and the pupils. This situation is really common for the indigenous communities in South Upi. People in the place seldom come out from their place which led them not to be exposed to other dialects.

Teacher H also encountered the same situation as she narrated “Sometimes, we encounter a language barrier too. When you explain something [concepts], you need to translate it [in their mother tongue] so you will be able to connect them with the lesson.” Furthermore, *Teacher A* shared “Another thing I experienced is that the children [learners] can hardly communicate with me in

Tagalog [much more with English]. You must speak in their mother tongue [to have a common understanding of what you are trying to expound].”

Undoubtedly, the revelations of the teacher-participants on language barriers are one of the challenges they encountered in the area which they believed to hamper learning. The above-cited statements acknowledged the study of Lariosa, Diendo, and Espinosa (2022) that an accurate message during the lesson results from effective communication. Even with the burning desire of the teachers to teach the students, teachers are not free from experiencing barriers in delivering the goods to the students. Most of the teachers shared during the interview that barriers in communication are their common issue in the instruction of the lessons. They shared that most of their students are IPs, and they don't have any background in their dialect, which makes it difficult for them to deliver instructions.

I.1.2. Light and Hope in the Midst of Struggle

This sub-theme entails the positive or light experiences faced by teachers in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas. Basically, it's the experiences that lightened up the situations they encountered in the area. These involved experiences that served as their light and hope.

Teachers' life in the remote is unbearable and strenuous. However, the participants reflected on the constructive and encouraging situations they experienced. As a result, they uncover meaningful life lessons that they used while still on this arduous path of career. These were grouped into categories and were also given titles based on the responses of the teacher-participants provided. Such as simple people with big hearts; prospects for growth; and the joy of seeing their pupils' dreams come true.

Simple People with Big Hearts

This experience was revealed to be predominant in the response of the four (4) teacher-participants. It defines the treatment of the co-workers and learners for the teachers and the support and assistance that they receive from the parents and the community as a whole.

People in the far-flung community are very welcoming and hospitable. Although, given that they're uneducated but they pay the highest respect to their teachers. They get themselves involved in school activities or programs. The following transcripts revealed that people in the far-flung areas are simple, yet they have big hearts for the teachers.

Cheerfully, *Teacher E* shared “At times you need the community people, they show their care, specifically if it concerns the school. Stakeholders [it refers to PTA, parents, lupon/elders, and barangay officials] of the school were also supportive.” It is truly imperative for teachers to get the necessary support from the community. Furthermore, Llego (2022) cited that parental involvement in education is indispensable and can meaningfully influence their child's academic success. When parents get involved in their child's education, they are more likely to help their children succeed in school and in life.

With gladness, *Teacher F* articulated “I'm happy that learners are also happy with my teachings. I am happy that the parents are also supportive. They even

gave us rice, and coffee during the time we slept in school. So, if you do your job well in school, they'll have no regrets about supporting you. In my eleven (11) years in the service, I barely think of transferring [to another school] because of the support I got from the parents." This participant seemed to be loved by the parents and community. Reflecting on his experience, one of his attachments to the place is the support he can get from the community and the parents. That support is earned by teachers through dedication and real hard work.

With a soft voice, *Teacher G* lamented that "there are so many positive experiences like supportive parents who didn't question my capability as a teacher. Pupils are very respectful. So, there's no regret on my part with the situation at hand." This teacher showed no regrets with the positive attitude and invaluable treatment she received from the community.

Likewise, *Teacher A* had a similar experience as he said "Yes, I do have a positive experience in teaching in GIDA. First, are the parents [who] are very easy to approach. Second, the pupils are kind and willing to learn. Lastly, working with underkind colleagues."

The amount of support that parents pay to the school and to the teachers has positive effects and impacts on their child's academic progress and these supports are incomparable. These declarations are identical to Durisic and Buniejivac (2017) that parents and families have a major impact on the success of the process of education and upbringing of children. The involvement of parents is related to their position at home (monitoring the learning of children), as well as participation in activities organized at school (parent-teacher conferences, volunteer activities, various forms of parental activism, workshops, and seminars for parents.

Prospects for Growth

Teachers have utilized their experiences, either the good or the bad, as an opportunity to develop themselves. This part refers to teachers' innate quality to acquire more skills, techniques, and valuable life lessons for them to thrive in this chosen field. Their passion and dedication to teaching have stepped to even greater heights due to the meaningful experiences they encountered.

Rubbing her both hands, *Teacher E* looked at the ceiling and said "Getting with the people is the first [positive experience]. My confidence to mingle with other Tëduray was boosted." She further noted that "I was able to develop managerial skills where I can say I am capable of leading. It serves as an opportunity for me to help not just my co-IPs but also myself that I discovered that I can also be a leader."

Additionally, *Teacher D* came up with a straightforward answer and she said "Yes, my positive experience is that I learned more while I am teaching. I was able to teach myself to be more confident, patient, and to be always optimistic [in life]." Truly, this participant revealed that our experience teaches us to become the best version of ourselves.

Expressively, *Teacher C* uttered "Yes sir, of course! Because I strongly believed that everything happens for a reason. My positive experience is that I

develop within myself the spirit of love, joy, peace, patience, long-suffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, and temperance with colleagues, and with learners and parents.” Having developed these qualities as a teacher, we can generally state that the rewards of the teaching profession go beyond our expectations.

In the same way, *Teacher H* proudly shared “Of course! sir, amidst the struggles we still have positive experiences too. I’m happy that I was able to adapt to the [school] environment. In my six years of teaching there, I developed a love for the community, the people there, and the learners. I’m happy because I knew I was able to help them but also in their daily lives.” Surprisingly, teaching in remote communities is satisfying and very fulfilling.

Being able to witness your contributions, your wisdom, and the values you instill in the learners slowly taking its shape in the place and the lives of the people in the area is such a euphoria. Teachers made use of their struggles, woes, and pain in teaching to see the beauty behind these. These realities were pronounced by Javilla and Fabella (2019) in their study that the experience of teaching in a remote school and community has been personally and professionally rewarding and often life-changing. Working together as a family will produce a school climate that endorses positive student outcomes and improves job satisfaction.

The Joy of Seeing Their Pupil’s Dream Come True

One of the things that bring the teachers pleasure is seeing their pupils thrive and reach their goals in life. Teachers feel good when their pupils have achieved their dreams in life. Some of the deliberations are presented in the following transcripts.

A determined *Teacher B* shared “Those sacrifices I’ve made in the place have had good results. My former pupils who were once my achievers in class maintained it even in High School. There are those who landed in the Top 1 in Villamonte. These (experiences) gave me an inspiration that what I had worked hard in the place had finally paid off.” Of all the sacrifices that this teacher had encountered in his teaching career in the far-flung school, he was not expecting a monetary reward.

With enthusiasm, *Teacher F* happily recounted “I’m happy, happy because I can help far-to-reach children and slowly they are getting civilized. But thankfully God provided me with the diligence to endure the distance and for the direction, goal, or purpose that is to deliver learning to them [learners]. At times, I walked alone, I told myself *ganito talaga, fight lang dapat, laban lang!* because it is our profession wherever God placed us, we must do what we can. Teaching is also a ministry. So, thankfully because of my goal, I was able to do my part.”

Additionally, *Teacher E*’s face lit up as she narrated “I feel so happy now seeing all my pupils entering high school already. Unlike before that, I have Kindergarten pupils who are already 12 years old. So, when they graduate from elementary, they won’t be enrolling in high school anymore because they feel ashamed of their age. [For now] No more overage or out-of-school youth in the community.” During the grouped discourse, it appeared that the teachers are conducting a child mapping activity or also termed a child find activity in school that

minimizes the case of overage learners. Parents were informed that as early as five years, a child is eligible for kindergarten.

Teaching in remote areas is not just about difficulties as the teachers are slowly bringing change in the lives of the people. The above-cited narrations are like Lariosa et.al. (2022), where teachers have developed commitment and dedication to their vocation/mission. Thus, they have found reasons for staying in their respective schools as they found loving children and found a purpose in which teachers are being respected.

Theme II. Coping Strategies Used by the Teachers in Facing the Challenges Encountered

The following themes describe the coping strategies used by the participants in geographically isolated areas. Since difficulties are inevitable for teachers in the GIDA, they must also be equipped with strategies to deal with their situations effectively.

II.1. Social Support System

This theme describes teachers coping strategies through the support they received from the parents or community, peers, co-teachers, stakeholders, and government agencies. The parents of the learners, colleagues and superiors, barangay, local government agencies, and other partners were the main source of support for teacher - participants in remote schools. The support they extend to the school and the teachers is an important factor for the school to make progress. Therefore, this impression helped the teachers cope with their situation in the area. The following are narrated in the following transcript.

Encouragingly, *Teacher E* expressed “The lack of classrooms was resolved by strengthening the Parent Teachers Association. This way, they lead the projects in school. The conduct of monthly meetings strengthened communications with parents. This led the school to have a much safer classroom because it had a strong foundation and was built with stronger construction materials. Unlike before the foundations were just [made of] bamboo trees. But when the parents were already organized much safer classrooms were built.” Initiating projects like makeshift building facilities in far-flung schools requires massive efforts due to their location. Material can hardly be carried. However, with help and assistance coming from the parents, this participant has been able to build more spaces for learning.

On the other hand, *Teacher F* received parents’ support in other means. He stated “During bad weather, parents’ support helped me cope with the situation. They’ll help us carry our motorcycle to the other side of the river when it floods. But the situation now is quite good on that portion [river] because there’s already a tire path.” Evidently, the support of the parents to teachers is not just limited inside the school premises. They even help the teachers to reach the school, which is much more aggravated when the weather conditions are not fine. Furthermore, he added that “I also referred to past teachers and administrators of the school, and I learned from the tips and advice they shared with us. The government provided us with training on how to handle multigrade classes.” This participant revealed that he

consulted past teachers for him to gain insights that he can utilize to face his present condition and there was training already provided to them. In GIDA, schools usually have multigrade classes. This is due to an inadequate number of teachers assigned in the area. Multigrade set-up requires a different teaching instruction. The aid of training and seminar were basic elements to effectively facilitate this kind of set-up.

In the same way, *Teacher H* logically expressed “During heavy rains what I do is to call the volunteers that we cannot go to school. *Hindi naman ako superhero na kayanin ang mga baha o mga bagyo* and then I’ll ask permission from the supervisor that we cannot be in school. Of course, I think also of my safety because I have my family too. What if I die, right? *kahit bagyo or baha susuungin para doon sa learners*. Although that should be the case. But due to far distance, you must think about what is good [for you].” In heavy weather conditions, this teacher showed practicality. Occasionally, teachers will be absent from their classes for some important matters. However, they should be seeking permission from their superior. Also, this participant revealed that their volunteer teachers who were from the community already were also informed of possible absences for them to take over their class while they were not around. She also recounted that “We lack teachers too, sir, I coordinated with BLGU and LGU to augment the lacking *para may katuwang kami sa pagtuturo* or guide the 315 learners.” Volunteer teachers were highly advantageous for teachers assigned to remote schools with relatively bigger populations. As a result, the barangay and local government unit supported the school by funding these teachers.

Finally, the participants showed that they also get support from their respective departments, which are the MBHTE, their barangay, and the local government unit. This support was in the form of training and seminars, and the hiring of locally funded teachers which basically aimed to reduce the problems of inadequate teaching staff in isolated areas.

The above-cited realities are parallel with the study of Javilla and Fabella (2019) that you will need a certain amount of resilience and the ability to solve problems and find support from new people.

II.2. Problem-Solving Strategy

This theme refers to a structured method utilized by the teachers to directly address the problem they faced in geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas. This involved their sound and practical judgment to a particular scenario and applying the best possible solution that is just within their control. The following are their transcriptions:

Confidently, *Teacher H* is definite in her coping strategy. She reluctantly shared “For slow learners, we focused on 3Rs for them to learn something than nothing at all. They crowd in the classroom so what we do is just go on.” This suggests that learners in far-flung schools are slow which is attributed to various factors including their incredibly large class size. Thus, teachers are only teaching them basic skills like reading, writing, and arithmetic.

Additionally, *Teacher F* shared “A book was provided to us to lessen the burden on our part as a teacher handling both grades.” Fortunately, this participant was able to have his teaching material to effectively facilitate a multigrade class.

On the brighter side, *Teacher E* articulated “To cope with insufficient learning materials like books we surf online for resources since teachers had their phones and the signal is available too.” This statement suggests that far-flung teachers utilized online sources for their lessons.

In general, the participants directly addressed the problems they encountered as long it was only within their capacity to resolve. Problems are inevitable. Thus, the teachers developed their own techniques and mechanisms to ease their situations in the area. Romero (2016) supports the following narrations. She regarded teaching as a vocation, mission, and profession. Few are chosen for this calling. To accomplish this mission, we had to equip ourselves with knowledge, skills, and the right attitude to be effective teachers. Every child who enters our classroom has been entrusted to our care. We have the responsibility to mold them and help them become better persons and make their lives meaningful.

This coping style of the participants was described by Van den Brande et.al. (2020) as a problem-focused coping style. It is an attempt to control work stressors by defining and interpreting them, planning solutions, and choosing a course of action. A method that is an effective way to tackle life problems.

The narrations of the teacher-participants had different opinions with Gallego (2022) that teaching and community coping techniques are the methods they used to surpass the difficulties they faced in teaching and the community they served like improvising teaching materials and conducting home visitation.

II.3. Acceptance and Devotion to Work

The participant narrated that their coping strategy was acceptance and devotion to work. The acknowledgment they have of the nature of the teaching profession as a challenging task coupled with their dedication was instrumental in their coping mechanism. Below are their revelations:

A passionate *Teacher H* expressed “As a teacher and school head, you need to find all the ways to cope with the challenges of being a teacher in far-flung areas. You need to sacrifice everything because it is our job or duty to provide learning to the Tëduray.” This narration uncovered that this participant is also a school head. Having recognized her purpose, which is to educate her fellow Tëduray, made her cope with the situation she comes across. Equally, a very compassionate *Teacher A* added “I (was able to) cope with the challenges of teaching in GIDA because I am proud to be an IP. I want to share all that I have with my learners because I believe that education is important and, I love teaching in the mountains or distant communities.” Being an IP himself, this participant felt the need of the indigenous people for education. Loving his work in the mountains is enough reason for him to manage all his struggles in life as a teacher.

In addition, *Teacher B* stated “You really need to love your work and do your work/job as a teacher which is important. To do it, you must do your best in your job, and you will forget (all sacrifices and difficulties) *kaya mahalín ang trabaho.*”

In the same way, Teacher C further stated “I always motivate myself to love my work, love the people around me, to love the place where I belong. Because my purpose is to serve and not be served.” Motivating himself to love his work and the people around him is the factor he considered as his coping strategy. Guided by his self-determined purpose which is to serve helped him cope with his situation in the distant community.

Lastly, *Teacher E* stated “[To cope] First is acceptance and then having pledged to teach gave us the responsibility for our learners. From the very start, you knew the nature of this career.” Realizing the nature of a teaching career which entails sacrifices and struggles makes her cope with her situation.

Through difficult times one’s dedication can be tested. When the teacher overcomes the situation through acceptance and by remaining pure in their intentions, this teacher is a devoted one. The statements support the study of Javilla and Fabella (2019) that indicated although the teaching profession can be demanding, various ways exist to survive and thrive. Knowing yourself also means knowing how you react under pressure and thinking about how you will cope without your close buddies and family nearby.

Also, these ideas are referred to by Gallego (2022) as work consolations. He mentioned that despite the challenges of the public-school heads in remote areas, they have not denied that they have found comfort in serving. As they continue to serve, they find their journey in a remote area self – fulfilling for they have found their true mission in the world of academe. They found a new family with their peers, colleagues, and community. And mold them to be an artistic educator for they make use of their extra talent to bring quality education to all.

In general, these participants revealed that their coping styles are based on their beliefs about truth, norms, and just. This phenomenon is defined by Algorani and Gupta (2021) as a meaning-focused coping style that employs cognitive strategies to process and make sense of the meaning of a situation. Accordingly, it involves religion, spiritual beliefs, beliefs about justice, values, and existential goals that may influence someone’s tendency to exhibit a meaning-focused coping style.

II.4. Burning Desire to Help

This sub-theme describes the motivations of the teachers in far-flung schools. Based on their narrations, helping the learners, parents, and the community, in general, is one of their sources of motivation.

A kind-hearted *Teacher D* narrated “So, for me, it’s like I’m challenged with my learners and some of them are slow. I motivate myself that at the end of the day, time will not be wasted and that they must acquire some knowledge.” Furthermore, she added that “I have seen the situation of the children wherein they really have less opportunity. That is why, it motivated me to help them uplift their learning (status).”

Teacher G in the same way said that “First is acceptance and then having pledged to teach gave us the responsibility for our learners. From the very start, you knew the nature of this career.” In the first place, this participant had already

embraced the fulfilling nature of the teaching profession. This prepared her to accept the job wholeheartedly.

Positively, *Teacher H* shared, “As my motivation in teaching in that far-flung area, I want to help the young IPs because I am an IP too by sharing with them what I have learned. I want them to be educated because as a teacher it’s our responsibility to share because we know that they are slow learners there, so why not do your best? So, that they can learn from you. Every child has the right to be educated.” This participant showed compassion towards her co-IPs and that she has a responsibility to mold them to be educated and share with them what she has.

Similarly, a compassionate *Teacher E* mentioned “I am motivated in this profession because I prefer to help my co-Tëduray to make them aware of the positive causes of education. I am motivated too because it’s the place for me where I can perform the profession I have chosen. Our home before was just behind the school in our barangay but it’s the way of God so I can help my co-Tëduray in the area.” Certainly, this participant exhibited utmost concern for her co-Tëduray. As most of the Tëduray in the mountains considered education to be of less priority and importance.

These statements were like Brillantes and Nebria (2021) who emphasized also that teachers felt deeper connections and attachments to the learners that made them feel the fulfillment of being a teacher specifically to IPs.

On the contrary, a purpose-driven *Teacher F* verbalized that “One thing that motivates me is my work or profession itself as a teacher. There is a purpose why I am in this area. I am not really forced by circumstances because I am happy with my wholehearted ministry in the place. One more thing is faith, this is the job given to me (by God), so I need to do my part, my obligation. Seeing the needs of the community for education motivates me.” Purpose, faith, and the needs of the community are the motivations of the participants.

In the same way, the motivation of *Teacher A* is extrinsic. He said “The one that motivates me is my family, they were always there to support me. They are even telling me that I should be helping the children in GIDA schools because unlike in the schools nearby, they have performing learners and adequate teachers to teach them.” Motivated by his family, who have supported him all throughout, this participant was determined to teach in the far-flung school.

These statements revealed that teachers in geographically challenged communities are truly committed to their chosen profession. In this way, it motivated them to work efficiently even with lots of difficulties. This supports the statement of Altun (2017) who described teacher commitment as a motivational force that inspires them to invest more time and energy in student achievement. This willingness to promote student accomplishment inspires teachers to seek ways to enhance the teaching profession and establish an effective learning environment to allow students to reach their goals. Teacher commitment is a crucial factor that impacts student achievement. Committed teachers devote themselves to their students, school, and teaching profession. When teachers are involved in developing their teaching profession, they can influence student accomplishment.

Teachers with high levels of commitment also motivate students to get involved in school activities.

In general, the participants demonstrated that their motivation for teaching is their passion itself. Borrowing the statement of Serin (2017), passionate teachers know that it is their responsibility to encourage students and they are always interested in their development. Passionate teachers work with enthusiasm, constantly increase their devotion and commitment and they believe in the importance of their job. This motivation served as the participants' coping mechanism in facing the obstacles in GIDA.

Theme III. Insights, Recommendations, and Aspirations of the Teachers in GIDA

The following emerging themes pertain to the insights, recommendations, aspirations, and reasons behind painstakingly teaching in geographically challenged communities. There were three sub-themes such as yearning for a brighter future, for one's own good, and the noble intentions of a teacher.

III.1. Yearning for a Brighter Future

This theme describes the teachers who are taking a stand for a brighter future ahead of them. Taking a stand that their situations will become better if the government can provide them with enough teachers, classroom buildings, infrastructures, and sufficient learning materials knowing that these things are essential to provide learners with a favorable learning climate. Three categories fall under this theme which was grouped according to how it was verbalized by the participants. This includes additional teachers, additional buildings, learning resources, and infrastructures.

Additional Teachers

This category describes the participants' recommendations for additional teachers. Seven participants came up with this recommendation. The following are their transcriptions:

A hopeful *Teacher D* stated "More regular teachers should be deployed to remote areas because usually, parents did not finish their studies or were uneducated at all. If there is, it is still not enough to help the school. So, it is one of the needs of the school to have [additional] regular teachers because the help of volunteers is really insufficient." Consequently, this participant is assertive of her recommendation that additional teachers are needed in far-flung schools. Similar to *Teacher G*, who also said that "[An additional] regular teacher [is recommended] because it's the need of the school.

Far-flung schools are less attractive for teachers. This is what *Teacher H* acclaimed "We need additional teachers because few are only attracted to far-flung schools because it's very far. I hope there will be teachers that the department will assign there to meet the needs of Bangsamoro learners."

A very explicit *Teacher C* shared "Yes sir, and to be specific the government or the agency should pay attention to schools in GIDA. Just like ... deployment of

regular teachers” Stipulating that additional teachers for GIDA schools should be given attention by the government. Likewise, *Teacher F* also mentioned, “I wish that the department will pay attention to us and add more regular teachers that have the same language orientation as the place so they can easily understand the learners.”

With composure, *Teacher E* enunciated “I recommend to BARMM MBHTE that applicants who are native to the place should be prioritized in the selection [process of hiring teachers]. In our place, there are board passers [licensed holders] who were not able to acquire an item [regular permanent position in the government]. These professionals had genuine care for the place because it is already their family that they are serving.” Remarking that the department will employ locality of teachers’ deployment to avoid teachers seeking for transfer after a year or two in other nearby schools.

These recommendations confirmed the statement of Llego (n.d.) that the deployment of teachers to geographically isolated communities is an effective way to address the problem of accessibility to basic education. Similarly, the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers (1966) recognized that advancement in education depends on the qualifications and ability of the teaching staff and that education is an essential factor in the economic growth of the nation as a productive investment of vital importance.

Additional Buildings

Classroom buildings were necessary for teachers and learners. In most cases, it motivates the learners and the teachers even more if they feel comfortable with their classroom. Four participants mentioned that additional classrooms or classroom buildings subsidized by the Department of Education or MBHTE is one of their great concerns. Below are the transcriptions:

A very grateful *Teacher E* took the opportunity to thank the ministry for the very first time, their school received a school building. She expressed “I thanked BARMM-MBHTE for giving us a new school building because it served as motivation for learners. So, with that, all I have to ask is a renovation from BARMM.” One of the reasons that may bring happiness to teachers is school buildings. This implies that it is one thing that they really wished and longed to have in their respective schools.

Learning is best facilitated when you are in a comfortable situation and atmosphere. Although learning can happen anytime and everywhere. But it is much more acceptable for teachers and pupils to have a conducive space. In this way, learning can take place meaningfully and effectively.

Teacher C said that “the government or the agency should pay attention to schools in GIDA. Just like the provision of school buildings. Similarly, *Teacher G* also said that “[I recommend for a] government building because most of our classrooms are just makeshift. We have 1 government building “*pero yung kahoy pa gud sir*” and only grades 1 and 2 can be catered in there. By having that, the learners will be motivated that they can feel support from the government, and they’ll support the school too.” With old and dilapidated buildings present in farflung

schools, receiving support from the government for things like school buildings is seen to be of great importance because it can also motivate the learners as well as strengthen community involvement in the school.

A very firm *Teacher H* expressed that “as my recommendation to lessen the work of the teachers there [far-flung area], due to the lack of classrooms I want the MBHTE or DEPED to give us additional classrooms.” She asserts that it has become one of the additional workloads and burdens for teachers in school to initiate a makeshift building for the learners and she believed that an additional government classroom will resolve this perennial concern of the teachers.

A favorable classroom environment suggests an effective teaching and learning process. Adequate classroom buildings contribute to the holistic progress of the learners. This is why, teachers in the far-flung school are very much concerned about the physical status of their school, particularly their classroom. In response to such dilemmas of the teachers, the Department of Education crafted the Last-Mile Schools Program to address the gaps in geographically isolated schools. Accordingly, among the indicators used in identifying a school as among the Last Mile Schools involves a school having less than four classrooms and with makeshift or nonstandard rooms (Llego, n.d). However, the participants revealed that classroom building is still one of the existing problems they struggle with.

Learning Resources

These include the materials of the learners like notebooks, papers, pens and pencils, computers, and other teaching materials. Five participants shared the same sentiments. Below are the transcriptions.

Teacher C strongly urged that “the government or the agency should pay attention to schools in GIDA. Just like the provision of learning materials.”

The same is true with *Teacher D* when she said, “Perhaps for concerned governments, (agencies), and individuals when it comes to teaching and learning materials, the remote areas should be prioritized.” Similarly, *Teacher E*, conveyed that “The Barangay should have an activity in a year where they will be giving learning materials like pencil and paper as it really helps the learner.” Learning materials are significant and one of the basic resources that learners must have enough supplies with. It is very useful in their day-to-day activities inside the class.

Shortly, *Teacher H* enumerated that “Additional classrooms, teachers, and learning materials that are applicable for learners were all my recommendations.” Contextualizing materials that suit the learners’ needs and backgrounds is very beneficial to schools in remote areas. This led the teachers to devise their own materials for teaching and learning to really address the applicability of the lesson to the learners for the best results.

A technologically oriented *Teacher A* revealed that “[I dreamed] to have computers be made available in school so learners can keep abreast with schools on the highways.” Nowadays, technology offers a variety of learning perspectives. It gives the learners access and the opportunity to learn beyond what is just being taught in school. This participant believed that it is imperative for learners to learn the basics of computers such as turning on and off the computer, typing and/or

encoding, and making PowerPoint presentations. In return, teachers can make their teaching more interesting and engaging.

These statements were congruent with Leocadio (2023) far-flung areas often lack the resources necessary for effective teaching, thus teachers have to improvise and find creative ways to teach their students. Moreover, teachers may not have access to basic necessities, particularly potable water, and electricity.

Infrastructure

Based on the insights of the participants, transportation is one thing they really find challenging. Their recommendations involve the construction of bridges, improving means of transportation, and electricity.

Teacher F shook his hands and said “I would also like to call our DEPED and DPWH to give us a bridge on the river as it will ease the transport of materials or supplies, commodities for the school which is really expensive due to the struggle of travel. So, all in all, I hoped it would be realized.” This participant revealed that due to the rugged road going to school, the transport of supplies and commodities going to school becomes costly. It is not the distance that the teachers are paying for the transport of materials, it’s the amount of hard work that the drivers get to safely deliver the goods and supplies to the school.

In the same way, *Teacher H* said, “For me, I aspire *na magkaroon ng magandang daanan papuntang school* to easily deliver quality education in the place and then materials for the schools’ improvement and development will be easily transported, as well as bridges in the rivers so that during flood we will not anymore experience difficulties, because I encountered almost getting drowned due to heavy rain one time that we went home.” It is common for far-flung teachers that their lives are at risk, especially when they have to cross a flooded river. This teacher aspires to have a much safer road going to school where there is no hazard they will encounter. Subsequently, *Teacher C* had the same sentiment wherein he said that the “Government should also improve the means of transportation to lessen the burden on teachers.”

On the other hand, *Teacher G* pointed out that “Electricity is one thing, so, during programs we can also use projectors because our solar power source cannot suffice it. Wherein at times, we want to show learning videos but then we cannot make it.” This participant would also like to share something new with the learners which is hindered by the unavailability of electricity in the place. Truly, life in the mountain school is not easy. You must teach with what are available resources at hand. You have to utilize indigenous materials that are readily available in the place.

The teachers aspired to have access to basic infrastructures such as bridges, road scraping or road improvement to lighten their burdens on transportation and also electricity as it is one of the basic needs of the schools in the far-flung areas for their printers and laptops and cellular phones. The results support the recommendation of Gallego (2022) that the officials from the Local Government Unit may direct the barangay to create an ordinance to cover the safety and security of the teachers in terms of road signs, road clearing, and

assigned officials or barangay *tanod* within the school vicinity. They should also be provided with necessary incentives such as additional hazard pay or accident insurance. In addition, a policy on wellness programs on both physical and mental health may be organized by the respective DepEd districts, particularly for the de-stressing of the teachers assigned in remote areas. He further stated that teachers must upgrade their ways of managing the school in order to cope with the different challenges they encounter by partnering with non – non-government parties that may help them to abridge the scarcity of teaching materials they face. Apart from being the agents of change, teachers must continue their undying dedication to service to foster an ambiance of good teacher-student relationships despite the challenges encountered. They should also be more creative in presenting the lesson to bring back students' interest in school, most especially in far-flung communities.

Finally, the Global Coalition to Protect Education from Attack (2014) stresses that teachers play a fundamental role in enlightening and educating children to become desirable constituents of their respective communities. The state therefore should provide hard work and resources to keep teachers secure and in good condition so that they can also perform well their duties as teachers.

III.2 For One's Own Good

This theme pertains to teachers' aspirations for themselves as professionals and as teachers. These include their aspirations for promotions; their aspiration to transfer to another school; and their aspirations for salary increase and additional incentives. The transcriptions fall into three categories namely: career advancement, transfer of school; and salary increase and additional incentives.

Career Advancement

Two of the participants revealed that they aspire to better their positions as teachers. Below are their statements:

With a sense of uncertainty, *Teacher E* opined "Yes, for myself where I am handling school, I need to improve myself of course! I am also longing for a promotion because the school has growing needs and I needed to fully support the school's development and the learners." This participant aimed for the teacher's promotion for the school's benefit and the learners because she can have more resources to support the needs of the school, particularly for its development.

Additionally, *Teacher F* conveyed "I aspire to be given a chance for promotion from teacher to at least teacher 2. I'm not even asking for more." Due to limited slots for a teacher's promotion in the ministry, this teacher was not asking for a higher position although he is a school head and the same a classroom teacher.

The results conveyed that the teachers in far-flung schools aspire to progress in their careers as teachers. To be given a chance or slot for promotions is enough explanation to recompense their sacrifices and efforts to

deliver quality education, particularly in remote areas. The following revelations are defined in Section 5, Article XIV of the Constitution provides that the State shall enhance the right of teachers to professional advancement and ensure that teaching will attract and retain its rightful share of the best available talents through adequate remuneration and other means of job satisfaction and fulfillment.

Moreover, the Republic Act (RA) No. 4670, or the Magna Carta for Public School Teachers also recognizes that the advancement in education depends on the qualifications and ability of the teaching staff, and declares it a policy of the State to promote and improve the social and economic status of public school teachers, their terms of employment and career prospects to attract and retain in the teaching profession more individuals with proper qualifications.

Transfer of School

These described the teachers' aspiration to transfer to nearer and much more accessible schools. Here are some of their statements:

Teacher H cheerfully said, "I aspire for myself to be transferred *"Inshaallah"* to much nearer schools and *"yung iba naman ma-assign doon para fair naman"*.

Looking at the ground, *Teacher G* sadly expressed "I aspire to be assigned to near schools wherein much accessible and not difficult to reach."

Lastly, *Teacher F* eagerly shared "I aspire to be transferred to a nearby school since I've been there for 11 consecutive years." Apparently, no matter how long this participant stayed in his school assignment he aspired to transfer to another school.

The above-cited statements were found parallel with Quejada and Orale (2018) who contended that no matter how teachers wish to be assigned permanently to far-flung schools, teachers are still looking forward to better assignments closer to their homes and families. This has been looked forward by teachers to be assigned to lowlands near their loved ones.

Increase in Salary and Incentives

Just like any other profession, teachers in far-flung areas have desired more incentives to compensate for their incomparable dedication and service in teaching. Below are their statements:

As a volunteer teacher in the far-flung school, *Teacher A* shared "For me, the LGU and BLGU where a far-flung school is located should help implement or provide good education by increasing volunteer teacher's honorarium." Truly, the services rendered by the volunteers are far more interesting to note. Minimal remuneration of a very uphill struggle is no joke for a teacher. Thus, this participant aspired for an increase in their compensation.

Furthermore, with faith, *Teacher D* retorted "Yes, I hope that they (the department) will look at the abilities (struggles and pains) of the teachers (in

far-flung) so that even if the position won't move at least just the salary will increase and also hazard pay.”

Generally, the following revelations are indications that the life of teachers in isolated and geographically distant communities is not simple. Although their narrations have already been stipulated in Republic Act 4670 - Magna Carta for Public Teachers, Article III, Section 19 that, in areas in which teachers are exposed to a hardship such as difficulty in commuting to the place of work or other hazards peculiar to the place of employment, as determined by the Secretary of Education, they shall be compensated special hardship allowances equivalent to at least twenty-five percent of their monthly salary. However, this provision was not applicable to volunteer teachers as they have not yet acquired permanency in teaching.

III.3. Noble Intentions of a Teacher

To wish for someone to become successful in their chosen endeavor, and/or become happy for someone's achievement exhibits nobility. Teachers are among the noblest people that we know. The following transcriptions demonstrated this act:

With so much passion, *Teacher A* expressed “I want all IP learners to become successful in their dreams and I would also want to be an example to them. I want to educate young mind IP learners because I am also an IP and most especially, I love the people in the community.” This participant has the same page as that of the people, so, he aspired them to be successful just like him. Equally, *Teacher D* calmly said “Perhaps, it's easy to say, “no choice” but as a teacher no matter how hard it is I took an ought for this, and I want to help my co-IPs.”

An optimistic *Teacher B* uttered “I have aspiration[s] too sir, I hope that there will be more professionals in the place so that I can be able to witness how my hard work paid off. I love my work and I think that whenever you do good things, good things will also come back to you. God will reward you back. It is all about being Godly and humane.” This participant considered the success of those within the community as a prize for his sacrifices. Driven by his faith in God, he aspired to do good because he believed that good things would likewise happen in return.

Also, a self-assured *Teacher E* opined “I stayed there due to love of work, and in fact, I really stayed there for good, I already built my home there to really give my services to children, and I have developed a love for children, for the place, and for the community. Also, I love my co-Tëduray, and I want them to have what I have today. While helping my family with their needs, I'm giving the community the services they[community] really needed from me.” This participant sincerely developed a strong attachment to the community where she teaches. Out of her determination to help her co-Tëduray, she had lived with them to give her service wholeheartedly.

A divinely inspired *Teacher C* said, “So, the very reason that I decided to stay as a teacher in the far-flung school is because I discovered my purpose which is to make a change – a change for the better.” As an agent of change, this participant is indeed determined to work for change.

In the same way, *Teacher H* also expressed “I have seen the situations of the learners there, as an IP, *mayroon akong [tinataglay na kakayahan] na pinakakailangan*

ng mga IP's sa ktulad ko na isang guro. That's the reason I stayed there even though it was hard. I will do everything for the sake of IP learners who need me. I even help them in processing documents, especially their birth certificate." This participant knew that her life in the remote area was not just about the struggles she experienced, it was also about her purpose and will to help the IPs. Seeing their conditions in the far-flung areas wherein they need her knowledge and expertise as a teacher.

Additionally, *Teacher G* rationally declared her answer in the form of a question that one of her reasons to teach in the area is "The learners, who will teach them?" Due to the lack of teachers, and the least appealing nature of the schools in far-flung areas, this participant is certain that nobody will replace her in the school if she no longer goes to the school.

In conclusion, the goals, and intentions of the following teacher-participants in teaching in remote areas are exceptional and deemed to be moral and genuine. Their life in the mountains is the epitome of living life to the fullest. This supports the idea of Gallego (2022) that teaching in remote schools defines the true meaning of a teacher's life. They are teachers who are considered the richest in terms of experience because of their commitment and passion for their chosen profession. Moreover, Gera (n.d.) also said that teaching has always been considered a noble profession that requires great passion. Being a teacher in the Philippines is a far more interesting story to tell. The challenges abound and one's passion can truly be tested, and if one prevails, a diamond in the rough emerges. The following participants also stated that they were staying in the school for the learners as they make a difference in the lives of the entire community. This proved the study of Durisic and Buniejivac (2017) that reaching out to the students and making a difference in their lives was important in deciding to remain in the teaching profession.

Conclusions

Teaching in geographically isolated areas is an actual test of a teacher's passion, dedication, and commitment to work. The teaching profession itself is already a challenging accountability but the situations of the teachers in far-flung areas are much worse. However, to be assigned in an isolated area doesn't just imply hardship as it appeared that teachers experienced fulfilling and life-changing scenarios. Based on the findings of this research I can conclude that far-flung teachers are exceptionally profuse with meaningful experiences and life stories. These experiences are not just stories of struggles and pains as others had believed and conceived but rather it has an exact opposite side of positivity. Educationally, this implies that teaching in far-flung schools in South Upi is not totally undesirable because, in the long run, you can uncover valuable experiences that can help you grow and thrive as professionals and as individuals. One's devotion, passion, commitment, and burning desire to help are of great worth in coping with the difficulties of far-flung teaching.

Participants revealed that they have been struggling with various obstacles in teaching in the area, but they received so much respect from the learners and community and the support coming from the parents is truly admirable. As a result, this lightened up their burdens in the place. Teachers educate and instill good values not just for learners

but also for the parents as most of them did not undergo formal instruction. Imparting to them the importance of education since most of the Indigenous People of South Upi - Tëduray have less concern and regard for education.

Additionally, the result of this research implies that by profoundly studying and realizing that teachers in the GIDA experienced a variety of uncomfortable means, the teachers in nearby schools will be inspired and motivated to do better as they have a favorable school environment. Novice teachers will have a broader concept of what it's like to be in far-flung schools. This could help them prepare emotionally, mentally, and physically.

The implications of the findings of this research will help the higher authorities craft and develop programs, activities, policies, and advance interventions that can alternatively reduce the burdens of teachers in distant communities. Finally, even though the teachers met so many challenges in teaching, their determination and passion for the students, and the community, had deeply influenced them to stay in the area. Indeed, they can move to nearby schools anytime they prefer to but their compassion towards the learners and the community is beyond comparison.

Recommendations

Fundamentally, the higher authorities particularly the Ministry of Basic, Higher and Technical Education (MBHTE) and school administrators should formulate and strengthen programs as well as policies that respond to the basic needs of the schools, learners, and teachers in far-flung areas. GIDA schools should be given school buildings and facilities. Moreover, immediate administrators and superiors should likewise provide instructional supervision and technical assistance to teachers assigned in the area. It is vital to fully ensure that learning provided in far-flung schools has achieved quality and competence. Teachers should be given the chance of promotions to compensate them and be granted additional incentives and remunerations like hardship allowance to give due recognition of their efforts.

This research highly recommends that neophyte teachers should be assigned to teach in the area since they are much stronger, healthier, and younger. However, a more experienced one should be designated as their school head. On the contrary, the old teachers should guide and nurture beginning teachers in the school.

Furthermore, the Local Government Units should improve the roads going to the schools. Teachers' lives are at stake when crossing flood rivers, so this research recommends that a bridge should be created for the benefit of the learners and teachers. Lastly, Non-Government Organizations and other school associates should offer more interventions and material support for teachers to dispatch or even lessen their countless needs in the area.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study observed the following ethical principles by Halai (2006). The researcher obtained informed consent from all those who were directly involved in the research. This principle adheres to a larger issue of respect to the participants so that they are not coerced into participation and have access to relevant information prior to the consent. Hence, the researcher prepared the consent-to-participate form containing the goals of the study and the rights of the participants including the risks, benefits, and a clause stipulating that their participation is voluntary, and they have the right to withdraw from the study.

Based on the confidentiality of information shared and the anonymity of the participants, this principle is concerned with offering respect and protection through assurance that the information shared will be solely used for research purposes only and that their identities will never be revealed to protect them. Typically, this is done through the use of code names such as Teacher A, Teacher B, and so on.

The third principle conveys that the researcher is expected to provide the participants with an outline of the risks and benefits. Reciprocity requires the researcher to compensate the participants for their time and effort. All the information relative to risks and benefits is expected to be provided in summary in the consent form.

Acknowledgments

With deep appreciation and sincere thanks, I would like to acknowledge the people who directly and indirectly helped me go through all the struggles to be able to complete this study:

My family for their advice and endless support in all aspects of my life including my educational quests.

I desire to thank my adviser, **Dr. Alfonso B. Mana-ay**, for his dedication, remarkable support, and assistance. He is incredibly lavish with his time. His guidance in this process has been a great manifestation of persistence.

I would like to express gratitude to **Dr. Tarhata S. Guiamalon** for her indefatigable support and reinforcement and her incredible contribution to my academic pursuits.

My deepest appreciation to members of the panel committee for their incomparable contributions and positive criticisms of the actualization of this research.

I express my sincere gratitude to **Marilyn G. Billones Ph.D** for her time and efforts in editing and improving my manuscript.

My immense thanks to our Division Superintendent, **Madam Bai Meriam A. Kawit, Al-Hadja**, and District Supervisor, **Alejandro Intar** for their guidance, supervision, and approval of the conduct of this study which contributed to the success of my thesis.

My biggest appreciation to the far-flung teachers who willingly and eagerly participated in this study.

Above all to the Triune God who is the source of strength and knowledge.

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